

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF IN-PLANE BRAID DISTORTIONS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BRAIDED COMPOSITES USING STOCHASTIC TOOLS AND FINITE ELEMENT MODELLINGM. Gautam¹, R. Shah², C. Liu², W. Sampson¹, and P. Potluri^{1*}¹ School of Materials, University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom² School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, United Kingdom³ Axon Automotive, Northampton, United Kingdom* Corresponding author (prasad.potluri@manchester.ac.uk)**Keywords:** Braiding, In-plane distortions, Stochastic Analysis, Finite Element Modelling**ABSTRACT**

In this paper, three types of braided composites each with different in-plane distortions, with a mean braid angle of 45° braid angle have been produced, to study the effect of in-plane distortions on the tensile behaviour (in axial direction) of braid composites. The first type of braid composite contained distortions introduced during preform manufacturing, handling and lay-up process; the second and third of composites had these distortion but in addition each also contained tailored distortions. The in-plane distortions of these three types of braid composite in terms of changes in braid angle, and braid axis deviation has been studied using stochastic tools. In addition the axial tensile behaviour of three types of composite produced is compared with a perfect braid, produced with help of finite element (FE) software (Abaqus CAE), using a unit cell shell based model. This paper also develops an algorithm to automatically determine the braid angle which is an optimised version

1. INTRODUCTION

With an ever-increasing use of fibre-reinforced composites in automobile industry, challenges also persist of incorporating Carbon fibre-reinforced composites (CFRP). These include: high cost of carbon fibres, relatively low slow production speeds, use of pre-pregs with limited shelf life and high labour costs due to touch-time. Braiding, which can help in producing near-net shaped preforms at high production rates, combined with higher automation, can address many of the process-based problems. The carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CRPF) braid composites have been known to exhibit higher energy absorption properties with progressive failures, as compared to metals in tension (1) and under crush-mode (2) with the optimum chosen lay-up configuration; this is due to the ability of interlaced tows in a braid to shear in direction of deformation and undergo multiple fibre fractures.

Currently in the composite industry, where braiding machines are not incorporated in production line, pre-braided sleeves are draped over mandrels, which are then passed on to the composite manufacturing stage. This process can incorporate distortions in the preform, especially for longer lengths of core. The distortions can also be introduced when the fabrics are draped or during tow placement over curvatures, as observed in (3). An example of such distortions has been shown in Figure 1, which shows a complex CFRP braided composite, where preforming was carried out by draping a braid sleeve over a soft core. Three different types of distortion: shear and wavy fibres are observed over longer lengths and highly localised distortion is observed around the beam edges and bends. In this paper, three type of braided composites parts were produced to determine the effect of different types of distortions on the axial properties of braided composites and compared with a perfectly formed braid formed in the finite element software: Abaqus CAE.

Figure 1: Complex CFRP braided composite beam with different distortions: Sheared, Wavy and highly localised

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. BRAID SAMPLE MANUFACTURING

The braided preforms were manufactured using a 48 carrier Cobra maypole braiding machine, as shown in Figure 2. A one inch diameter mandrel was over-braided with 12K carbon tows, obtained from Torayca, with a 45° braid angle. The specification of the carbon tows has been reported in Table 1. Post braiding, the carbon fibre over-braid was slit along the length of the mandrel, as shown in Figure 2. The tubular preform upon slitting was opened up to produce a flat preform and advanced to vacuum bagging process followed by resin infusion and curing. The tubular preform contained a single layer of braid.

Figure 2: (a) 48 carrier braiding machine, (b) 1" braid angle with 45° braid angle, and (c) Braid slit open along the length of the braid

Type	ρ (g/cm ³)	E_{xx} (GPa)	E_{yy} (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	G_{xz} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{yz}	X_T (MPa)	ϵ_{Tu} (%)
Fibre	1.8	230	15	10	5.23	0.2	0.2	4900	2.1
Matrix	1.15	2.5	-	0.94	-	0.34	-	67	2.4

Table 1: Fibre and Matrix Properties (4–7)

The preforms were infused with Crestapol 1260 resin system (properties reported in Table 1), which is a high temperature urethane acrylate resin from Scott Bader Company Ltd, which contains: Trigonox 239 (hardener) which is Cumyl hydroperoxide in 45% in solvent mixture (8) added to 2% by weight of resin, and a solution of cobalt octoate in styrene (Accelerator G) used as the accelerator (2% by weight of resin). The infused preforms were cured at room temperature, and post-cured at 80°C for 3 hours. In order to study the effect of distortions on the mechanical properties of the braid, three types of preform were manufactured. The first type of preform produced contained distortions, arising from preform manufacturing stage, to preform cutting, to stage involving flattening of tubular preform, to the handling of the preform up to the bagging process. This form of distortion in the preform has been referred to as: ‘Type 1 distortion’ in this paper.

Figure 3: Process of introducing Type 2 distortion

The second type of preform contained the Type 1 distortions, and in addition a controlled distortion was further introduced in the preform. This controlled distortion involved constraining the preform on 2 ends of the preform with the help of a high performance tape (width of 1 cm), as shown in Figure 3. Post constraining the edges, an area of: 1 cm X 1cm, at centre of one edge, outwards, giving it a pattern observed in Figure 3. This type of distortion has been referred to as ‘Type 2 distortion’ (T2D). The third type of composite also contained the Type 1 distortion, which were introduced due to the specimen handling & bagging process and in addition another type of distortion was introduced by constraining one end of the preform with tape (tape width of 1 cm) and shearing the fabric sideways, with a shear angle of $\sim 3^\circ$ (as shown in Figure 4). This type of distortion has been referred to as ‘Type

3 Distortion' (T3D). The distortion pattern observed in T2D preforms can be observed when a flat preform is draped over a curvature. The type of distorted pattern observed in T3D can usually be introduced when a pre-made braid sleeve is pulled over a core with long lengths, causing a warping effect along the length of the specimen.

Figure 4: Process of introducing Type 3 distortion

2.2. BRAID DISTORTION MEASUREMENT AND RESULTS

As the measurement of braid angle of a preform or a composite with larger area and longer lengths can be highly time consuming, in this paper the braid angles were detected automatically, using the algorithm shown in Figure 5, which was converted into a MATLAB (9) code. A similar algorithm has also been presented in the work conducted in (10). However, the algorithm in this paper aims at significant reduction of noise in the braid angle measurement.

Figure 5: Algorithm developed for automatic detection of the braid angle

The first step in automated determining of braid angle involved, importing the image of a braid taken from a high definition camera into MATLAB (9), and then converting this image from a ‘true colour’ image (*i.e.* image with Red, Green, and Blue Channels) to a grey scale image. Prior to this step the lighter and darker areas in the images were homogenised with rest of the light intensity of the image, by opening the image in the MATLAB (9) software. The level of homogenisation dictates the level of noise in the braid angle detection, however higher level of homogenisation also results in increasing the computational time. Followed by the image homogenisation, the edges in and around the interlaced tows were detected using the: Canny Edge Detection (CED) method presented in (11). In CED method, strong and weak edges in an image are detected, which differs significantly from other edge-detection methods (10). If the Canny Edge detection algorithm is compared with common edge detection algorithm, in most cases, the Canny algorithm has the best performance (12,13). The Canny Edge detection converts the RGB image into a binary image. This binary image is then further processed to remove noise (unwanted lines detected) and then further processed to Hough transform for braid angle detection.

Figure 6: Automated Braid Angle Detection using Canny Edge Detection and Hough Transform Function (θ is the braid angle)

The Hough transform (14) is a classical approach to find the parameters of lines in a binary image and is used in the MATLAB (9) code to determine the braid angle. The Hough transform, which maps each point in the image within the parameter space which could possibly produce image points that are located on an edge (15). It generates a series of lines using the set threshold, line length and the line gap. With the help lines generated, using a vertical axis angle can be measure of these intersecting lines. This angle is the same as a braid angle in case of braid, which is the angle subtended by interlaced tows with the vertical axis. The braid angle of three types of composites developed was measured only for the area of interest, which was cut into a coupon for the tensile test (as shown in Figure 6). The distortion in the braid axis was measured using Image J?? (16), for the region of interest, where the points were first plotted at the intersection points along all the braid axis present in the image. These points were then imported into MATLAB (9) software to determine the distortions with reference to vertical axis passing through the first point of interlacement. This was repeated for each of the braid axis.

Figure 7: Cumulative probability distribution of: (a) Braid axis deviation for all three braid distortions, and (b) Braid angle for all three types of distortions (Note: μ is average and σ is standard deviation)

The automated determined braid angles using MATLAB (9) code for each all three type of composites developed and the mapped in-plane braid distortion have been represented in form of cumulative probability curves as shown in Figure 7, where at least +500 data points for braid axis deviation and +100 data points for braid angle. As it can be observed from Figure 7(b), that the mean braid angles were around 45°, where for T1D composites, at 90% probability, the braid angles range between 44° - 47°, whereas for T2D composite there is 90% probability that the braid angles are between 30° - 55°, whereas for T3D specimen there is 90% probability that the braid angles are between 35° - 55°. However, in T2D specimen there is only 10% probability that the braid angles will be in between 30° - 39°, and for T3D composite there is was only 10% probability that the braid angle is \sim 35°. For deviation in the braid axis, as observed in Figure 7 (b), there is 90% probability that the braid axis deviates between: -8% to 20% for T1D composite, between: -700% to 100% for T2D composite, and between: -75% to 50% for T3D composite. However there is only 20% probability that the braid axis deviations are in between: -8% to 0% for T1D composites, -700% to 300% for T2D composites, and -75% to 0% for T3D composite.

2.3. TESTING

The tensile tests were carried out conforming the ASTM standard: D3158 (17). Five specimens of each type of composite produced were tested. The tensile tests were carried out in accordance with. All tested specimens had lengths of 250 mm, a nominal width of 40 mm and had 50 mm long end tabs at both the ends. The tab material used was a glass fibre fabric-epoxy based FRP composite with a thickness of 1.5 mm and the composite tabs were bonded to the flattened braided composites using 3M Scotch-Weld adhesive, and cured at the 65° C temperature, with uniform pressure applied on both faces (front and back) of the specimens. In the tensile tests, axial strains were recorded using the Instron video extensometer. In this method four dots are applied to the composite surface, two dots along the specimen length for axial strain measurement and two along the width for transverse strain

measurement. The displacements between these pair of dots when subjected to load, is recorded by the video extensometer is recorded and converted to strains.

2.4. FEM

In order to compare the behavior of distorted composites with a perfectly formed braid, a finite element model of the 45° braid unit cell composite was constructed, using planer shell. The advantage of using this modelling technique is computationally significantly less expensive than modelling an actual unit cell with 3D elements. The unit cell width (W) and height (H) were 3.4 mm and 6.8 mm respectively. This modelling technique is capable predicting in-plane properties of the braid composites, but it cannot predict the through thickness properties. In this modelling technique, the planer shell is partitioned as per the topology of the unit cell. Three types of region are partitioned as shown in Figure 8, with tows only region, tow cross-over region, and matrix rich region. In the tow only region there are $+\theta$ tow and $-\theta$ tow (whichever is on top or bottom depends on the unit cell topology); the cross-over region has a matrix layer and a $+\theta$ tow or $-\theta$ tow layer (depends from which tow it is crossing from), and a matrix only layer.

Type	E_{xx} (GPa)	E_{yy} (GPa)	E_{zz} (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	G_{xz} (GPa)	G_{yz} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{xz}	ν_{yz}
Non-crimped Tow	141.3	3.3	3.3	4.6	4.6	1.0	0.25	0.25	0.82
Crimped Tow	105.3	3.3	3.3	4.3	4.5	0.9	0.5	0.02	0.81

Table 2: Elastic Properties of Crimped Tows

Figure 8: (a) 45° braid composite with unit cell outlined, (b) Shell Model for 45° braid

This braid unit cell shell modelling technique has also been used in literature (18). The volume fraction of the tows was determined using a micrographs and was determined to be 0.58 ± 0.06 . The elastic properties and the strength of composite tow were determined from the equations presented in literature (19–21), and have been reported in Table 2 and Table 3. The fracture energy for FEM has been reported as 89 J/m^2 for matrix and for composite tows (crimped and straight) has been reported in

Table 4, obtained from (18).

X_{It} (MPa)	X_{Ic} (MPa)	X_{Lt} (MPa)	X_{Lc} (MPa)	$S_{in-plane}$ (MPa)
2870	3306.4	56	50	37.4

Table 3: Strength of Crimped Tows

Type	Longitudinal Tensile Fracture Energy J/m^2	Longitudinal Compressive Fracture Energy J/m^2	Transverse Tensile Fracture Energy J/m^2	Transverse Compressive Fracture Energy J/m^2
Non-crimped Tow & crimped tow	81.5	61	0.31	1.55

Table 4: Fracture properties of composite tows (18)

The crimp in the tows as a result of undulations were incorporated in the determining the elastic property of the composite tow using the analytical equation presented in (22). The crimp angle was determined to be $10.50^\circ \pm 0.75^\circ$. Upon meshing of the model, periodic boundary condition was applied to the edges of the unit cell, to ensure continuity between the neighboring unit cell. If x and y as Cartesian coordinates are parallel to the unit cell, the periodic boundary conditions can be expressed in terms of displacement vectors: U_1 and U_2 as a pair of master nodes, which are related to the nodes (as a result of mesh and element generation) on the opposite edges of the unit cell. The ‘Equation’ tool in Abaqus CAE was used to pair the nodes at opposite end such that: $u(H, y) - u(0, y) = U_1$ and $u(x, W) - u(x, 0) = U_2$. The axial tensile load was applied on the master nodes: U_1 and U_2 , with $U_1 = (\delta, 0)$ and $U_2 = (0, u_2)$, where u_2 is obtained from FEM from the condition of zero average stress in direction perpendicular to braid axis. The reaction nodes were extrapolated from master nodes.

3. RESULTS

3.1. MECHANICAL TEST RESULTS

The axial tensile behaviour of the three types of composite developed have been reported in Figure 9 & Figure 10, where the all types of composite specimen tested, depicted similar tensile behaviour: exhibiting an initial elastic zone, followed by yielding and a plateaued region (representing the non-linear zone) followed by failure. The plastic zone saw necking of the specimen with increasing strains, however each type of composite specimen exhibited different onset of necking and neck formation. In Figure 9, for T3D specimens, post drop in the axial stress, saw compressive strains. This is due to the specimen going through multiple tow fractures near the ends of the specimen (post neck formation) while still undergoing extension, resulting in the region below, which also contains the gauge length, undergoing compression rather than extension. The stress-strain behaviour of all three composites produced has been compared with stress-strain behaviour of a perfectly formed braid, using unit cell finite element modelling with help of periodic boundary conditions (as described in previous section). On comparing the stress-strain curves in Figure 11, it can be seen that the FE generated curve for a perfectly formed braid lies within the cloud of experimental curves (representative curves).

Figure 9: Tensile behaviour of three types of composites produced: (a) Type 1 Distortion, (b) Type 2 Distortion, and (c) Type 3 Distortion

If the axial chord modulus of all three types of composites is compared, it can be observed that the mean chord modulus values remained the same for all three types of composites ranging between 13.4 GPa - 13.9 GPa. However, if the standard deviation values are compared, largest standard deviation value was observed of 2.0 GPa by T2D specimen followed by standard deviation value of 1.7 GPa exhibited by T3D specimens, and least standard deviation values of 0.63 GPa shown by T1D specimens. Looking at the axial strength values, a similar trend was also observed where all three composite specimen depicted similar axial strengths but, with significantly differing standard deviations. The highest standard deviation values were shown by T2D specimens with values of 23.28 MPa, followed by T3D specimens showing standard deviation values of 21.51 MPa, and T1D specimen showing the least standard deviation values of 14 MPa. On comparing the axial strains to failure, Type 2 depicted highest axial strain to failure, possibly due to the curved (sinusoidal) in-plane distorted pattern, imparting the braid higher necking than a Type 1 braid. The Type 3 distortion showed least strain to failure due to the distortion pattern being more aligned towards the load axis, as the shearing of braid by $\sim 3^\circ$ along the length caused one set of tow (in - Θ direction) to get more aligned along load axis with limited neck formation in comparison with Type 1 and Type 2 composites. The trend observed as in case of axial strength and modulus was also reflected in strain to failure values where, braid types with higher distortions also exhibited higher deviation in their values.

Figure 10: (a) Axial Modulus and (b) Axial Strength values of all three types of composites tested (Note: σ refers to standard deviation) and FEM results

All samples with higher distortions showed higher deviation among them, the high deviations in the chord modulus and axial strength values could have arisen from specimen manufacturing process. Although the process of introducing distortions for all types of specimen was kept same, exact same distortions could not be mimicked within all types of specimens. A drop of 16.7 % was observed when the axial chord modulus values from distorted composites were compared with the FEM generated perfectly formed braid with a value of 16.2 GPa, helping in inferring that the effect of distortions due to handling of braid preforms and other two type of tailored distortions in the composite have a significant effect on the axial properties of the composite. The axial strength values obtained from FEM for a perfectly formed braid cannot be compared, as the model did not include the non-linearity observed due to shearing of tows. However initial axial strength predicted by the FE model was 101.9 MPa, which is lower than the axial strength predicted by all three types of distorted composites. The predicted failure is derived from Hashin's transverse tensile failure (23). The model does not incorporate geometric and material non-linearity.

Figure 11: Comparison of FEM generated curve with representative stress-strain curves, (b) Stress Contours of Unit Cell – FEM at failure (Hashin's Tensile Matrix Failure)

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, three types of 45° braided composites were produced each with distinct distortions, to determine the effect of in-plane distortions on the axial properties of the braided composites. The axial properties of these distorted composites were compared with a perfectly formed braided unit cell, formed in a finite element modelling software. An algorithm was also developed (optimization of currently available techniques) to determine the braid angles automatically with significantly less noise and more accuracy.

The effect of in-plane distortions was observed to be insignificant on the axial modulus of composites with all three types of composites exhibiting similar values, primarily due to the mean braid angle being around 45° for all three composites. However, on comparison with a perfectly formed braided unit cell using FEM, a reduction in axial modulus of 16.7% was observed in the axial modulus of distorted composites.

Experimentally, the effect of in-plane distortion was more pronounced in the non-linear region, with each type of composite showing different lengths of plateaued stress region. This plateaued region was a result of necking behaviour arising from shearing of the tows along the load axis due to tensile loading. Each type of composite showed different necking behaviour before failure, also showing different mean axial strain to failure. Overall, composite with higher in-plane distortion showed much higher deviation in the axial properties among the same specimens tested. Further investigation into the effect of overall braid angle (lower and higher than 45° braid) with in-plane distortions of the braided composites on tensile and transverse behaviour of braided composites is currently ongoing as part of this project.

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REFERENCES

1. Pickett AK, Fouinneteau MRC. Material characterisation and calibration of a meso-mechanical damage model for braid reinforced composites. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf.* 2006;37(2):368–77.
2. Hull D. A unified approach to progressive crushing of fibre-reinforced composite tubes. *Compos Sci Technol.* 1991;40(4):377–421.
3. Lightfoot JS, Wisnom MR, Potter K. Defects in woven preforms: Formation mechanisms and the effects of laminate design and layup protocol. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf.* 2013;51:99–107.
4. Herrera-Ramírez LC, Cano M, Guzman de Villoria R. Low thermal and high electrical conductivity in hollow glass microspheres covered with carbon nanofiber–polymer composites. *Compos Sci Technol.* 2017;151:211–8.
5. Torayca. Technical Data Sheet No. CFA-005 - T700. 2002.
6. Crestapol. Crestapol 1260. 2017.
7. Hancox NL, Mayer RM. Mechanical Properties of Random and Fabric-Reinforced Resins. In: Hancox NL, Mayer RM, editors. *Design Data for Reinforced Plastics: A guide for engineers and designers.* Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands; 1994. p. 55–95.
8. AkzoNobel. Material Safety Datasheet - Trigonox 239. 2012.
9. Mathworks. MATLAB version R2014a. Natick, Massachusetts; 2014.
10. Liu Y, Kyosev Y. Automatic Analysis The Braiding Angle of the Braided fabrics Using Image Processing. In: *The 22nd International Conference - STRUTEX 2018.* 2018. p. 63–8.
11. Canny J. A Computational Approach to Edge Detection. *IEEE Trans Pattern Anal Mach Intell.* 1986;PAMI-8(6):679–98.
12. Pellegrino FA, Vanzella W, Torre V. Edge detection revisited. *IEEE Trans Syst Man, Cybern Part B.* 2004;34(3):1500–18.
13. Nguyen TB, Ziou D. Contextual and non-contextual performance evaluation of edge detectors. *Pattern Recognit Lett.* 2000;21(9):805–16.
14. Hough PV. C. Method and means for recognizing complex patterns. U.S. patent 3069654, 1960.
15. Aggarwal N, Karl WC. Line detection in images through regularized hough transform. *IEEE Trans Image Process.* 2006;15(3):582–91.
16. Abramoff MD, Magalhaes PJ, Ram SJ. Image Processing with ImageJ. *Biophotonics Int.* 2004;11(7):36–42.
17. ASTM. Standard Test Method for In-Plane Shear Response of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials by Tensile Test of $\pm 45^\circ$ Laminate - ASTM D3518. 2018.
18. García-Carpintero A, Herráez M, Xu J, S. Lopes C, González C. A Multi Material Shell Model for the Mechanical Analysis of Triaxial Braided Composites. *Appl Compos Mater.* 2017;24(6):1425–45.
19. Daniel IM. *Engineering mechanics of composite materials.* 6th ed. New York: Oxford University Press; 1994.
20. Yong Li X, Reifsnider KL. Micromechanical Modeling of Composite Compressive Strength. *J Compos Mater.* 1993;27(6):572–88.
21. King TR, Blackketter DM, Walrath DE, Adams DF. Micromechanics Prediction of the Shear Strength of Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Matrix Composites: The Influence of the Matrix and Interface Strengths. *J Compos Mater.* 1992;26(4):558–73.
22. Potluri P, Manan A, Francke M, Day RJ. Flexural and torsional behaviour of biaxial and triaxial braided composite structures. *Compos Struct.* 2006;75(1–4):377–86.
23. Hashin Z. Theory of fibre reinforced materials. NASA CR 1974; 1972.